

Graph-Based Numerical Method for Safety Category Assessment in Industrial Control Systems

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Abstract

Safety category assessment according to EN ISO 13849-1 in industrial control systems traditionally requires manual analysis of electrical schematics, making the process time-consuming and susceptible to interpretation variability. This paper presents a graph-based method in which electrical safety circuits are represented as directed graphs for structural analysis. Using a structured, machine-readable representation, the method identifies redundancy patterns, feedback-monitoring structures, and logic-level independence within safety-related control architectures.

The proposed approach performs automatic path enumeration, redundancy detection, and preliminary category estimation, distinguishing between non-redundant architectures (Categories B/1) and redundant monitored architectures (Categories 3/4). Validation was conducted using 15 representative safety functions from the BGIA (Berufsgenossenschaftliches Institut für Arbeitssicherheit) Report 2/2008e as reference examples. The method achieved full agreement with reference structural classifications while maintaining execution times below 1 second per circuit. Additional perturbation experiments demonstrated conservative behavior under incomplete or corrupted graph encodings, with no unsafe escalation from non-redundant to redundant category assignments.

The framework provides reproducible, traceable preliminary category evaluation as decision support prior to quantitative analysis. It does not distinguish between Categories B and 1, between 3 and 4, or classify Category 2, since these require reliability parameters or temporal information beyond static topology. The method bridges schematic documentation and quantitative SISTEMA validation, supporting integration into digital safety-engineering workflows.

Keywords: functional safety, EN ISO 13849-1, graph-based analysis, safety category assessment, automated verification, control system architecture

1 Introduction

Preliminary safety category assessment according to EN ISO 13849-1 remains a structurally interpretive task performed before quantitative Performance Level (PL) validation. Tools such as SISTEMA support quantitative assessment, but the preceding step - identifying category-relevant architectural properties from electrical schematics - is still largely manual, subjective, and difficult to reproduce, particularly for complex or customized architectures. Errors at this stage can propagate into costly redesign of machine electrical architectures. This work addresses the gap by formalizing category-relevant structural properties as computable graph conditions evaluated on circuit-derived representations.

The developed tool aims to assist engineers by numerically analyzing circuit topology and providing an initial category estimation based on structural features represented in a graph model. Specifically, the tool differentiates between:

- Categories 3/4, where the safety function is redundant and includes feedback, monitoring, or diagnostic coverage
- Categories B/1, where one or more of these structural conditions are not satisfied

Category 2 is not assessed automatically, as it may involve complex Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) logic or operator-dependent interactions that require contextual evaluation beyond the circuit's structure.

The method is therefore designed as a decision-support system, not a replacement for expert judgment. The final and detailed category determination (i.e., distinguishing between exact levels B, 1, 2, 3, or 4) should still be performed by the engineer using specialized tools such as SISTEMA. The primary focus of this approach is to achieve consistent and repeatable preliminary category detection, allowing early design verification and improved traceability of safety function evaluations.

The main contributions of this paper are:

1. A formal mapping of EN ISO 13849-1 architectural requirements to graph-theoretic properties, enabling repeatable structural category assessment.
2. A JSON-based representation that encodes electrical safety circuits in a machine-readable form suitable for automated analysis.
3. A graph-analysis procedure capable of detecting redundancy, feedback relationships, and logic-level independence directly from circuit topology.
4. A preliminary category estimation method (B/1 vs. 3/4) validated on standardized safety functions from BGIA reference documentation.
5. A workflow that increases documentation traceability and facilitates digital integration with SISTEMA and model-based safety tools.

The remainder of the paper covers background and related work (Section 2), methodology (Section 3), results (Section 4), discussion (Section 5), limitations (Section 6), and conclusions (Section 7).

2 Background and Related Work

2.1 Functional Safety Standards and EN ISO 13849-1

The design of safety-related control systems for machinery is governed by international standards that define requirements for risk reduction through reliable control architectures. EN ISO 13849-1 [1] provides the main framework for safety-related parts of control systems (SRP/CS), combining risk-based Performance Level determination with five architectural categories: B, 1, 2, 3, and 4. These categories express structural and diagnostic assumptions concerning single-channel or redundant architectures, fault detection, and fault tolerance.

EN ISO 13849-1 is applied alongside standards such as IEC 62061 [3] and IEC 61508 [4], which address functional safety using Safety Integrity Levels (SIL). In the machinery domain, EN ISO 13849-1 remains widely used because of its applicability to machine control systems and the availability of dedicated engineering tools [9]. The final Performance Level assessment requires several types of information, including architectural category, the mean time to dangerous failure (MTTFd), average diagnostic coverage (DCavg), and common cause failure (CCF) measures. However, not all of these quantities can be inferred from an electrical circuit diagram.

From a schematic perspective, the most directly observable properties are structural: signal paths, redundancy, feedback or monitoring connections, and the separation of logic channels. Other aspects, such as component reliability, diagnostic coverage, common cause failure resistance, software behavior, or periodic test sequences, require additional data or behavioral analysis. This distinction is central to the present work: the proposed method addresses only the structural part of category reasoning.

The relationship between categories and structural properties is summarized in Table 1. Categories B and 1 correspond to single-channel architectures and differ mainly in component selection requirements. Category 2 introduces periodic testing, which is temporal rather than purely structural. Categories 3 and 4 require redundant architectures with monitoring or diagnostic mechanisms, but differ in the completeness of diagnostic coverage and fault accumulation handling [7].

Table 1: Structural characteristics of EN ISO 13849-1 categories

Category	Channels	Redundancy	Diagnostics	Fault Tolerance
B	Single	No	None	None
1	Single	No	None	None
2	Single	No	Periodic	None
3	Dual	Yes	Partial	Single fault
4	Dual	Yes	Comprehensive	Accumulated faults

Consequently, static circuit topology can support preliminary discrimination between non-redundant architectures (Categories B/1) and redundant monitored architectures (Categories 3/4), but it cannot fully determine Category 2, distinguish

B from 1, or distinguish 3 from 4. This boundary is consistent with recent developments in model-based safety assessment, where behavioral and temporal properties are treated as separate modeling concerns rather than as features directly inferable from static structure [36, 38]. In particular, periodic testing and time-dependent diagnostic behavior require models that represent sequences, timing, or state evolution, which motivates the exclusion of Category 2 from the automatic structural classification proposed in this work.

2.2 Engineering Tools and Schematic-Based Workflows

SISTEMA, developed by the German Institute for Occupational Safety and Health (IFA), is one of the most widely used tools for EN ISO 13849-1 Performance Level verification [2, 9]. It enables engineers to model safety functions and calculate achieved Performance Levels based on component reliability data, diagnostic coverage, CCF scoring, and an already selected architectural category. Thus, SISTEMA supports quantitative validation, but it does not infer the architectural category directly from the electrical schematic.

This separation between structural interpretation and quantitative validation is important for the present work. The proposed method targets the preceding step: identifying whether the circuit structure contains category-relevant architectural patterns before parameters such as $MTTF_d$, DC_{avg} , and CCF are evaluated in dedicated tools. Recent tool-oriented and digital engineering workflows increasingly emphasize structured data exchange, but category-level semantic interpretation of circuit topology remains a largely manual task [9, 39].

This creates a practical gap in the assessment workflow. Before SISTEMA analysis can begin, engineers must manually interpret electrical schematics, identify safety function boundaries, determine whether redundant channels exist, and assess whether monitoring or feedback structures are present. This step is experience-dependent and may lead to inconsistent results, especially for modified, retrofitted, or non-standard machine architectures [7].

Risk assessment tools and vendor-specific safety design tools support other parts of the safety lifecycle, such as required Performance Level (PLr) estimation, component selection, and documentation management [6]. ECAD systems can additionally store structured information about components, connections, identifiers, and cross-references. However, these tools generally do not perform semantic reasoning over circuit topology to determine whether a safety function satisfies EN ISO 13849-1 category-relevant structural properties. Recent work on ECAD-based engineering automation suggests that structured circuit data can increasingly be extracted from design documentation, but automatic safety-category reasoning remains insufficiently addressed [9].

2.3 Model-Based Safety Analysis

Model-Based Safety Analysis (MBSA) provides mature approaches for automating safety reasoning from system models, including HiP-HOPS (fault tree and Failure

Modes and Effects Analysis (FMEA) synthesis), AltaRica and xSAP (formal failure-propagation analysis), the Architecture Analysis and Design Language (AADL) Error Annex, and component fault trees [8, 11, 13, 14, 16–19, 23, 24, 34, 35]. Recent reviews confirm MBSA as a diverse and active research direction [15, 36], with extensions toward time-aware [38] and AADL-based [37] reasoning. These methods operate on behavioral or annotated architectural models - a different starting point from the static, circuit-derived representations used here.

A related limitation has been discussed by Sun and Fleming [42], who argue that MBSA results depend on whether relevant safety-critical scenarios are represented in the input model in the first place. Their STPA+ methodology complements MBSA by supporting the derivation of safety-relevant design information before formal verification. This observation is consistent with the motivation of the present work: before quantitative or behavioral safety analysis can be trusted, the structural assumptions encoded in the input representation must be made explicit, traceable, and suitable for subsequent assessment.

MBSA is therefore complementary to the proposed method: it supports deeper behavioral and failure analysis, whereas the present work targets the earlier schematic interpretation step before quantitative SISTEMA validation. Table 2 summarizes the positioning of the proposed method relative to the discussed MBSA approaches.

Table 2: Positioning of the proposed method relative to existing safety assessment approaches

Approach	Typical input	Typical output	Relation to this work
SISTEMA	Category + reliability data	Achieved PL	Quantitative validation
HiP-HOPS	Annotated system model	Fault trees, FMEA	Failure propagation analysis
AltaRica/xSAP	Behavioral model	Fault trees, verification	Formal safety analysis
AADL Error Annex	Architecture/error model	Error propagation	Model-based analysis
Proposed method	Circuit-derived graph	B/1 vs. 3/4 pre-assessment	Structural category support

Recent work continues to extend MBSA into model-based systems-engineering workflows. Hu et al. [44] integrated event-tree-based safety analysis within Systems Modeling Language (SysML) activity diagrams for space mission design, and Chu et al. [45] proposed automatic generation of dynamic fault trees from SysML models for embedded systems. Such advances confirm MBSA’s growing capability for behavioral and temporal safety reasoning, but reinforce that they address a different problem from the structural pre-assessment task addressed here.

2.4 Graph-Based Methods in Reliability and Safety Analysis

Graph representations are well established in reliability engineering, electrical engineering, and safety analysis. Reliability block diagrams, minimal path sets, minimal cut sets, connectivity analysis, and graph-based failure propagation methods all rely

on representing systems through components and their interconnections [25–28]. Electrical circuits also naturally map to graphs, where components correspond to vertices and control, power, or feedback relations correspond to edges.

These methods provide useful mathematical foundations for structural reasoning. Minimal path and cut-set concepts are closely related to redundancy and single-point-of-failure analysis, while Binary Decision Diagrams have been used for efficient reliability calculation and fault tree evaluation [27, 28]. Graph-based methods have also been applied to vulnerability and resilience analysis in infrastructure networks [30, 31], as well as to failure propagation and safety verification [12, 22]. These studies show that graph models are a natural and well-established representation for analyzing structural dependencies in technical systems.

Knowledge-graph and graph-neural-network methods address adjacent problems - hazard prediction in railway systems [40, 41], fault diagnosis in industrial processes [46], maintenance planning [47], and infrastructure resilience assessment [48] - but typically require historical data or learned representations, which is unsuitable for certification contexts requiring transparency and explicit traceability to normative requirements.

The present work therefore does not claim novelty in graph theory itself, nor does it propose a learning-based graph model. Path enumeration, connectivity analysis, and directed graph traversal are established techniques, and libraries such as NetworkX provide standard implementations for these operations [10]. The contribution lies instead in mapping specific EN ISO 13849-1 architectural requirements to computable graph properties: structural redundancy, feedback monitoring, and logic-level independence.

2.5 Automated Interpretation of Electrical Schematics

Automated interpretation of electrical schematics has become increasingly relevant due to the development of ECAD systems, digital engineering workflows, and machine-readable exchange formats. ECAD tools such as EPLAN, AutoCAD Electrical, and related environments can store component identifiers, connection topology, device properties, and cross-references in structured or semi-structured formats. Standards for industrial system designation, such as IEC 81346, support consistent component naming and can facilitate automated processing of electrical documentation [5].

Several studies have investigated the extraction of analyzable models from electrical schematics. Schöbel et al. [20, 29] demonstrated automated conversion from electrical schematics to formal models for safety verification, showing that structural information can be extracted when schematics follow standardized conventions. Sun et al. [21] proposed methods for extracting component relationships from electrical schematics, while recent computer-vision-based approaches explore recognition of schematic symbols and circuit structures from image data [33]. These works establish that schematic-to-graph or schematic-to-model conversion is feasible.

Recent diagram-recognition research shows that electrical diagrams can be decomposed into component, text, and connection layers, supporting the feasibility of future automated conversion from schematic documentation to graph representations [39]. This direction is complementary to the present work. Schematic extraction addresses

how to obtain a reliable structural representation, whereas the method proposed here addresses how such a representation can be interpreted with respect to EN ISO 13849-1 category-relevant structural properties.

Recent AI-based approaches also indicate that increasingly complex schematic-to-model workflows are becoming technically feasible. Neuro-symbolic methods have been explored for compliance checking of electrical control panels [49], while recent schematic-image-to-netlist approaches combine object detection, OCR, and vision-language components for automated netlist generation [50]. These methods address the extraction and compliance-checking side of the workflow. In contrast, the present work focuses on deterministic interpretation of an already structured circuit representation with respect to EN ISO 13849-1 category-relevant properties.

2.6 Research Gap and Contribution Positioning

The reviewed literature shows that several adjacent areas are well developed. EN ISO 13849-1 tools such as SISTEMA support quantitative Performance Level validation, MBSA methods support fault propagation and behavioral safety reasoning, graph-based methods support reliability and connectivity analysis, and ECAD-related approaches support extraction of structural information from electrical documentation. However, these areas do not directly address the specific task considered in this paper: automated structural pre-assessment of EN ISO 13849-1 category-relevant properties from circuit-derived graph representations.

Therefore, the research gap is not the absence of graph algorithms, model-based safety analysis, or schematic extraction methods in general. The gap lies in the lack of a reproducible method that connects these areas for a specific industrial task: translating EN ISO 13849-1 category-relevant architectural requirements into explicit graph conditions evaluated on circuit-derived representations. The contribution of this work is a standard-specific structural formalization and decision-support procedure intended as a layer before detailed SISTEMA analysis, not as a replacement for expert judgment, behavioral verification, or quantitative reliability assessment.

Recent standardization efforts in AI-enabled safety systems provide additional context for automated safety assessment approaches. ISO/IEC TR 5469:2024 [43] establishes principles for integrating artificial intelligence with functional safety life-cycles, addressing challenges in reliability, transparency, and verification of AI-driven safety analysis. While the present work employs deterministic graph algorithms rather than machine learning, this emerging standardization landscape suggests future opportunities for hybrid approaches combining rule-based structural reasoning with AI-based pattern recognition.

3 Methodology

This section presents a formal graph-theoretic framework for the structural analysis of safety-related control systems in accordance with EN ISO 13849-1. The proposed method transforms electrical circuit representations into directed graph models, enabling automated detection of architectural properties relevant to safety category determination. The methodology comprises four principal stages: (i) structured data

preparation, (ii) directed graph construction, (iii) algorithmic analysis of topological properties, and (iv) category estimation with result visualization.

Figure 1 illustrates the workflow of the proposed method, from schematic encoding and verification to graph construction, structural property analysis, and preliminary category estimation. The corresponding algorithmic implementation is summarized in Appendix A.

Fig. 1: Methodology flowchart illustrating the transformation from electrical schematics to preliminary category estimation through graph-based structural analysis.

3.1 Formal Problem Definition

Let a safety-related control system be characterized by a set of components $\mathcal{C} = \{c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n\}$ and a set of connections $\mathcal{E} = \{e_1, e_2, \dots, e_m\}$ representing signal, power, or feedback relationships between components. The objective is to determine structural properties $\mathcal{P} = \{p_{\text{redundancy}}, p_{\text{feedback}}, p_{\text{logic_redundancy}}\}$ that inform preliminary category classification according to EN ISO 13849-1.

Definition 1 (Safety Function Chain). *A safety function chain \mathcal{S} is defined as an ordered sequence of components $(c_{i_1}, c_{i_2}, \dots, c_{i_k})$ such that there exists a directed path from an input element $c_{i_1} \in \mathcal{C}_I$ to an end effector $c_{i_k} \in \mathcal{C}_M$ through logic and output*

elements, where \mathcal{C}_I , \mathcal{C}_L , \mathcal{C}_O , and \mathcal{C}_M denote the sets of input, logic, output, and end effector (motor/actuator) components, respectively.

Definition 2 (Structural Redundancy). *A safety function exhibits structural redundancy if and only if there exist at least two node-disjoint paths π_1 and π_2 from the input set \mathcal{C}_I to the end effector set \mathcal{C}_M , such that:*

$$V(\pi_1) \cap V(\pi_2) \cap \mathcal{C}_L = \emptyset \quad (1)$$

where $V(\pi)$ denotes the vertex set of path π , excluding common start and end nodes. This condition ensures that redundant channels do not share logic elements that could constitute single points of failure.

Definition 3 (Feedback Monitoring). *Feedback monitoring is present if there exists at least one edge $(c_j, c_i) \in \mathcal{E}$ where $c_j \in \mathcal{C}_O \cup \mathcal{C}_M$ and $c_i \in \mathcal{C}_L$, representing a backward signal flow from output or actuator elements to logic elements for diagnostic purposes:*

$$\mathcal{E}_{feedback} = \{(u, w) \in \mathcal{E} : \tau(u) \in \{\text{Output}, \text{EndEffector}\} \wedge \tau(w) = \text{Logic}\} \quad (2)$$

where $\tau : \mathcal{C} \rightarrow \mathcal{T}$ is the component type function.

3.1.1 Normative Mapping and Necessity Conditions

Definitions 1–3 formalize a subset of the architectural requirements of EN ISO 13849-1 Table 10. Their relation to the normative clauses is summarized below.

- **Single-fault tolerance (Cat. 3, clause 6.2.6; Cat. 4, clause 6.2.7):** The structural redundancy condition (Def. 2) encodes the requirement that a single component fault must not lead to loss of the safety function. Logic-disjointness of π_1 and π_2 is a *necessary* condition: if two channels share a logic element, that element constitutes a single point of failure. However, logic-disjointness alone does not *guarantee* single-fault tolerance, because faults affecting shared inputs, shared power supplies, or common environmental factors are not captured by the graph model.
- **Fault detection (Cat. 3, clause 6.2.6; Cat. 4, clause 6.2.7):** The feedback monitoring condition (Def. 3) provides a necessary structural prerequisite for fault detection: a diagnostic channel from output or actuator elements back to logic elements must exist for monitoring to be possible. It does not quantify diagnostic coverage (DCavg), which requires component-level failure mode analysis.
- **Common-cause failure (Cat. 2–4, Annex F):** The logic-disjointness condition partially addresses one of the Annex F scoring items (separation/diversity at the logic stage) but does not replace the full Annex F scoring procedure, which requires assessment of physical separation, diversity of design, environmental robustness, and competence-related measures.

Accordingly, the conjunction $p_{\text{redundancy}} \wedge p_{\text{feedback}} \wedge p_{\text{logic_redundancy}}$ should be interpreted as a *necessary structural precondition* for Category 3 or 4 classification, not as a

sufficient condition. Failure of any of these conditions excludes Category 3/4 on structural grounds; their satisfaction indicates that the quantitative requirements (MTTFd, DCavg, CCF score) should be evaluated next in dedicated tools such as SISTEMA.

3.2 Source Material and Data Representation

The source data for method validation originate from reference safety functions documented in the BGIA Report 2/2008e [7], which provides standardized examples of safety circuit architectures spanning EN ISO 13849-1 Categories B through 4. Each circuit was systematically encoded into a structured JavaScript Object Notation (JSON) format that captures both component attributes and interconnection topology.

3.2.1 JSON Schema Specification

The JSON representation comprises two primary data structures that fully characterize the safety circuit:

Elements Array.

Each component $c_i \in \mathcal{C}$ is represented as a JSON object containing the following mandatory fields:

- **id:** Unique alphanumeric identifier conforming to IEC 81346 designation principles (e.g., “B1”, “K1”, “Q1”)
- **type:** Component classification $\tau(c_i) \in \mathcal{T}$, where $\mathcal{T} = \{\text{Input, Logic, Output, EndEffector}\}$
- **I0:** Input/Output designation for signal flow directionality
- **description:** Human-readable component description for traceability

Connections Array.

Each connection $e_j \in \mathcal{E}$ is represented as a JSON object specifying:

- **from:** Source component identifier (tail of directed edge)
- **to:** Target component identifier (head of directed edge)
- **type:** Connection classification $\gamma(e_j) \in \Gamma$, where $\Gamma = \{\text{control, power, feedback, safety_output}\}$

This structured representation enables deterministic software processing and provides a well-defined interface for potential future integration with ECAD systems capable of automated data export. The schema enforces referential integrity, requiring that all component references in the connections array correspond to defined elements.

3.3 Graph Construction

The JSON representation is transformed into a directed graph $G = (V, E)$ using the NetworkX library [10], a Python package for complex network analysis. Vertices V correspond to circuit components and directed edges E represent signal or power connections with associated metadata.

3.3.1 Graph Model Formalization

Definition 4 (Safety Circuit Graph). *A safety circuit graph is a labeled directed graph $G = (V, E, \tau, \gamma)$ where:*

- $V = \mathcal{C}$ is the vertex set corresponding to circuit components
- $E \subseteq V \times V$ is the edge set representing directed connections
- $\tau : V \rightarrow \mathcal{T}$ is a vertex labeling function mapping each vertex to its component type
- $\gamma : E \rightarrow \Gamma$ is an edge labeling function mapping each edge to its connection type

The graph construction procedure parses the JSON input and instantiates the corresponding NetworkX DiGraph object with appropriate node and edge attributes. Component type information is preserved as node attributes, enabling type-based filtering during subsequent analysis phases.

3.3.2 Visualization

Interactive visualization is implemented using the PyVis library, which generates HTML-based graph renderings employing the following visual encoding scheme:

- **Node color:** Encodes component type - Input (yellow), Logic (green), Output (orange), EndEffector (blue)
- **Edge style:** Solid lines for forward signal flow (control, power, safety_output), dashed lines for feedback connections
- **Edge color:** Distinguishes connection semantics - control (black), power (red), feedback (gray), safety_output (orange)

This visualization bridges the schematic domain familiar to electrical engineers with the computational graph domain, facilitating verification of encoding accuracy and supporting engineering interpretation of analysis results.

3.4 Analytical Procedures

The constructed graph undergoes a series of algorithmic analyses to extract structural properties relevant to EN ISO 13849-1 category determination. These procedures, formalized in Algorithm 1, are executed automatically upon graph construction.

3.4.1 Path Enumeration

All simple paths from input vertices to end effector vertices are enumerated using depth-first search with cycle avoidance. For a graph G with input vertex set $V_I = \{v \in V : \tau(v) = \text{Input}\}$ and end effector vertex set $V_M = \{v \in V : \tau(v) = \text{EndEffector}\}$, the complete set of safety function paths is:

$$\mathcal{P}_{\text{all}} = \bigcup_{v_i \in V_I} \bigcup_{v_m \in V_M} \text{SimplePaths}(G, v_i, v_m) \quad (3)$$

where $\text{SimplePaths}(G, s, t)$ returns all paths from source s to target t that visit no vertex more than once. The cardinality $|\mathcal{P}_{\text{all}}|$ indicates the total number of distinct

signal routes through the safety system, providing an initial indicator of architectural complexity.

3.4.2 Redundancy Detection

Structural redundancy is assessed by identifying parallel paths between input-effector pairs. For each pair $(v_i, v_m) \in V_I \times V_M$, the redundancy predicate is evaluated as:

$$\text{Redundant}(v_i, v_m) = \begin{cases} \text{True} & \text{if } |\text{SimplePaths}(G, v_i, v_m)| \geq 2 \\ \text{False} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Path independence is subsequently verified by computing the vertex intersection of identified paths. For paths π_1 and π_2 , output-stage independence requires:

$$V(\pi_1) \cap V(\pi_2) \cap V_O = \emptyset \quad (5)$$

where $V_O = \{v \in V : \tau(v) = \text{Output}\}$. This verification ensures that identified redundant channels do not share common output elements that would invalidate the redundancy claim under single-fault conditions.

3.4.3 Feedback Detection

Feedback or monitoring connections are identified by detecting edges that establish backward signal flow from output-stage components to logic components:

$$E_{\text{feedback}} = \{(u, w) \in E : \tau(u) \in \{\text{Output}, \text{EndEffector}\} \wedge \tau(w) = \text{Logic}\} \quad (6)$$

The boolean feedback indicator is then:

$$p_{\text{feedback}} = (|E_{\text{feedback}}| > 0) \vee (\exists \text{ path from } V_O \cup V_M \text{ to } V_L) \quad (7)$$

This condition captures both explicit feedback edges (labeled with $\gamma(e) = \text{feedback}$) and implicit monitoring paths that may traverse intermediate components.

3.4.4 Logic Redundancy Assessment

Logic-level redundancy is evaluated by analyzing whether logic nodes receive inputs from multiple distinct input channels:

$$\text{LogicRedundant}(v_l) = \begin{cases} \text{True} & \text{if } |\{v_i \in V_I : \exists \text{ path } v_i \rightsquigarrow v_l\}| \geq 2 \\ \text{False} & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

where $v_i \rightsquigarrow v_l$ denotes the existence of a directed path from input v_i to logic node v_l . This condition verifies that logic elements perform cross-comparison of signals from independent sensor channels, supporting the diagnostic requirements of Categories 3 and 4.

3.4.5 Category Estimation

The extracted structural properties are combined through a rule-based classification that maps topological characteristics to preliminary category assignments. The decision logic implements the following mapping:

$$\text{Category} = \begin{cases} 3/4 & \text{if } p_{\text{redundancy}} \wedge p_{\text{feedback}} \wedge p_{\text{logic_redundancy}} \\ \text{B}/1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

This binary classification distinguishes between:

- **Category B/1:** Single-channel architectures, or multi-channel architectures lacking feedback monitoring or logic-level redundancy
- **Category 3/4:** Redundant architectures with feedback monitoring and logic redundancy, satisfying the structural prerequisites for single-fault tolerance

Category 2 is explicitly excluded from automatic assignment because its defining characteristic - periodic functional testing initiated by the control system - requires temporal and behavioral information that cannot be inferred from static circuit topology. Similarly, the distinction between Categories B and 1 (based on component selection and well-tried principles) and between Categories 3 and 4 (based on diagnostic coverage completeness) requires quantitative reliability parameters (MTTFd, DCavg) beyond the scope of structural analysis.

3.4.6 Computational Complexity

The computational complexity of Algorithm 1 is dominated by the path enumeration phase. For a graph with $|V|$ vertices and $|E|$ edges, simple path enumeration between a source-target pair has worst-case complexity $O(|V|!)$ for dense graphs. However, safety circuit graphs are typically sparse with bounded degree, yielding practical complexity of $O(|V| \cdot |E|)$ for realistic circuits. The redundancy and feedback detection phases operate in $O(|V|^2)$ and $O(|V_L| \cdot (|V_O| + |V_M|))$ respectively, which are dominated by the path enumeration cost.

For the validation dataset comprising circuits with $|V| \leq 15$ components, execution time was negligible (< 1 second per circuit on standard hardware).

3.5 Result Representation

Analysis results are generated in two complementary formats designed to support engineering decision-making and documentation requirements for functional safety compliance.

3.5.1 Tabular Summary

A structured summary report is produced in tabular format (exportable to Excel/CSV) containing the following fields for each identified safety function:

- Safety function identifier (input \rightarrow effector mapping)
- Number of paths detected ($|\mathcal{P}_{(v_i, v_m)}|$)

- Redundancy status ($p_{\text{redundancy}}$)
- Feedback presence (p_{feedback})
- Logic redundancy status ($p_{\text{logic_redundancy}}$)
- Estimated category (B/1 or 3/4)
- Structural remarks and identified components

This output format facilitates direct comparison with reference categories from standards documentation and supports integration into SISTEMA project files and safety documentation workflows.

3.5.2 Interactive Graph Visualization

The PyVis-generated HTML visualization provides an interactive environment for structural exploration:

- Nodes are draggable for layout optimization
- Hover interactions display component attributes and connection details
- Redundant branches are visually distinguished through layout grouping
- Feedback loops are highlighted with distinctive edge styling

This visualization serves both verification purposes (confirming encoding accuracy against source schematics) and communication purposes (supporting design reviews, audits, and SISTEMA documentation).

3.6 Threats to Validity

Several factors may influence the validity and generalizability of results, which are addressed through appropriate methodological controls and explicit scope limitations.

3.6.1 Internal Validity

Manual JSON Encoding

Circuit models were created through manual transcription from schematic diagrams, introducing potential for human error. This threat was mitigated through:

- Systematic encoding procedures following a defined checklist
- Visual verification comparing generated graph visualizations against source schematics
- Independent review of a subset of encodings

To partially assess sensitivity to encoding imperfections, a perturbation-based robustness study was performed in which edges, nodes, and monitoring relations were systematically removed or modified. Results are reported in Section 4.6.

Ground Truth Reliability

Reference categories from BGIA Report represent expert consensus but may contain ambiguities for boundary cases. The validation focuses on structural property detection rather than exact category matching, reducing sensitivity to reference interpretation differences.

3.6.2 External Validity

Structural Analysis Scope

The method evaluates only topological properties extractable from circuit structure. Properties requiring quantitative data or behavioral analysis are explicitly excluded:

- Diagnostic coverage percentage (DCavg)
- Component reliability parameters (MTTFd, B10d)
- Test interval timing for Category 2
- Software logic behavior in programmable systems
- Common cause failure scoring

Implicit Feedback Representation

Industrial schematics frequently represent monitoring functions implicitly through mechanical linkages, mirror contacts, or internal relay diagnostics. Such features require explicit modeling to be detected by the algorithm, potentially leading to false negatives for feedback detection in circuits where monitoring is present but not explicitly drawn.

Static Topology Limitation

Graph-based analysis captures structural relationships but not dynamic or sequential behavior. Safety functions involving time-dependent logic, state machines, or conditional execution paths cannot be fully characterized through static analysis alone.

3.6.3 Construct Validity

Category Granularity

The binary classification (B/1 vs. 3/4) represents a deliberate methodological choice reflecting the limits of structural analysis. Finer distinctions (B vs. 1, 3 vs. 4) require information beyond topology:

- Categories B and 1 differ in component selection principles, not structure;
- Categories 3 and 4 differ in diagnostic coverage completeness and fault accumulation handling.

Category 2 Exclusion

Category 2 architectures employ single-channel structures with periodic testing - a temporal property not detectable from static graphs. Automatic Category 2 assignment would require behavioral model analysis or explicit test sequence annotation.

3.7 Validation Protocol and Encoding Verification

The validation procedure followed a structured protocol designed to assess agreement with reference structural classifications. Additionally, a perturbation-based sensitivity analysis was conducted to evaluate robustness against incomplete or corrupted graph encodings by systematically modifying graph structure and re-evaluating classification stability.

3.7.1 Test Dataset

Eleven circuit examples were selected from BGIA Report 2/2008e [7], yielding 15 distinct safety function chains for analysis. The selection criteria ensured coverage of:

- All structural category patterns (B, 1, 2, 3, 4)
- Single-channel and dual-channel architectures
- Presence and absence of feedback monitoring
- Various input device types (position switches, safety switches, emergency stops)
- Different output configurations (contactors, frequency inverters)

3.7.2 Correctness Criteria

A classification was considered correct when the tool accurately reproduced the structural properties specified in EN ISO 13849-1 Table 10 for the reference category:

- **Number of channels:** Single ($n = 1$) vs. redundant ($n \geq 2$)
- **Monitoring presence:** Required for Categories 2, 3, 4
- **Single-fault tolerance:** Structural capability to maintain safety function after one fault

Deviations were systematically analyzed to determine root cause: structural limitations of the method, incomplete information in source diagrams, or encoding errors. For each safety function, the following procedure was executed:

1. Source schematic extraction: Electrical diagrams were extracted from BGIA Report 2/2008e documentation in standardized format.
2. Manual adaptation: Minor modifications were applied to ensure unique component identifiers conforming to IEC 81346 conventions (e.g., B1.1/B1.2 replacing duplicate B1/B2 designations) and explicit representation of feedback paths where implicit in original documentation.
3. JSON encoding: Circuit structure was transcribed into JSON format according to the defined schema 3.2.1
4. Encoding verification: Graph representations were validated against source schematics through visual inspection, verifying:
 - All safety-relevant components appear as graph vertices with correct type assignments
 - All signal and power connections are represented as directed edges
 - Feedback paths are explicitly modeled where present in source documentation
 - No spurious vertices or edges were introduced during encoding.

Figures 2 - 5 present side-by-side comparisons of adapted schematics and generated graph representations for representative examples.

5. Automated analysis: The graph analysis algorithm 1 was executed to extract structural properties
6. Property comparison: Detected structural properties were compared against EN ISO 13849-1 Table 10 requirements for the reference category

7. Classification evaluation: Results were classified as correct match or deviation, with systematic analysis of any discrepancies

This multi-stage verification protocol ensured that classification outcomes could be attributed to algorithmic performance rather than encoding errors. The visual comparison step (item 4) served as a critical control against transcription mistakes, though complete elimination of encoding error risk would require automated ECAD-to-JSON conversion.

3.8 Method Summary

The proposed methodology establishes a formal, reproducible framework for preliminary safety category assessment based on circuit topology. By transforming electrical schematics into graph representations and applying algorithmic structural analysis, the method provides:

1. **Objective property identification:** Automated detection of redundancy, feedback monitoring, and output independence based on explicit graph criteria
2. **Transparent reasoning:** Category estimations traceable to specific structural features and algorithmic decision points
3. **Analyst independence:** Consistent results across different users given identical input encodings
4. **Documentation support:** Visual and tabular outputs compatible with engineering review workflows

The method is positioned as a decision-support tool complementing, rather than replacing, expert judgment and quantitative SISTEMA analysis. Its primary value lies in providing early-stage architectural validation and ensuring that fundamental structural requirements are satisfied before detailed Performance Level calculations are undertaken.

4 Results

This section presents the empirical evaluation of the proposed graph-based category estimation method. The validation study assesses the method's capability to detect structural properties relevant to EN ISO 13849-1 category determination, including redundancy, feedback monitoring, and logic-level independence. Results are presented for 15 distinct safety function chains derived from 11 reference circuits documented in BGIA Report 2/2008e [7].

4.1 Validation Dataset

4.1.1 Dataset Composition

The validation dataset comprises 11 safety circuits from BGIA Report 2/2008e, yielding 15 distinct safety function chains. This dataset was selected to provide comprehensive coverage of EN ISO 13849-1 architectural patterns, spanning Categories B through 4. Table 3 summarizes the dataset composition by reference category.

Table 3: Validation Dataset Composition by Reference Category

Reference Category	Circuits	Safety Functions	Structural Characteristics
B	1	1	Single channel, basic components
1	6	7	Single channel, well-tried components
2	1	1	Single channel, periodic testing
3	4	5	Dual channel, partial monitoring
4	1	1	Dual channel, comprehensive monitoring
Total	11	15	

The dataset includes circuits of varying complexity, from simple single-input single-output configurations (SF01, SF05) to multi-function circuits containing both single-channel and redundant safety functions within the same schematic (SF17, SF21). This diversity enables assessment of the method’s performance across the spectrum of industrial safety architectures.

4.1.2 Representative Examples

Four safety functions were selected for detailed analysis to illustrate the method’s operation across different architectural patterns:

- **SF05:** Single-channel architecture with one input device and one output path, representing Category 1 reference design
- **SF06:** Extended single-channel architecture with multiple input devices (push-buttons, emergency stop) and self-latching motor control, representing Category 1 with increased topological complexity
- **SF17:** Multi-function circuit containing both single-channel (emergency stop function, Category 1) and dual-channel (gate interlock function, Category 3) safety functions
- **SF18:** Dual-channel architecture with redundant inputs (B1.1/B1.2), logic-level redundancy, and explicit feedback monitoring, representing Category 3 design

Minor adaptations were applied to source schematics to ensure unique component identifiers conforming to IEC 81346 conventions (e.g., B1.1/B1.2 replacing duplicate B1/B2 designations) and explicit representation of feedback paths where implicit in original documentation.

4.2 Graph-Based Circuit Representation

Each safety function was transformed into a directed graph representation $G = (V, E, \tau, \gamma)$ following the methodology described in Section 3. The transformation preserves the logical structure of source schematics while exposing structural dependencies amenable to algorithmic analysis.

4.2.1 Transformation Fidelity

Graph representations were validated against source schematics through visual inspection, verifying that:

1. All safety-relevant components appear as graph vertices with correct type assignments
2. All signal and power connections are represented as directed edges
3. Feedback paths are explicitly modeled where present in source documentation
4. No spurious vertices or edges were introduced during encoding

Figures 2–5 present side-by-side comparisons of adapted schematics and generated graph representations for the four detailed examples.

Fig. 2: SF05 (Reference Category 1): Single-channel architecture with position switch input (B1), safety relay logic (K1), contactor output (Q1), and motor end effector (M1). Graph analysis identifies one path with no redundancy or feedback.

4.3 Structural Property Detection

The graph analysis algorithm (Algorithm 1) was executed on each safety function to extract the three structural properties defined in Section 3.1: path redundancy ($p_{\text{redundancy}}$), feedback monitoring (p_{feedback}), and logic-level redundancy ($p_{\text{logic_redundancy}}$).

4.3.1 Path Enumeration Results

Table 4 presents the structural metrics extracted for the four representative safety functions. The path count $|\mathcal{P}_{(v_i, v_m)}|$ indicates the number of distinct signal routes from each input to the end effector.

(a) Adapted schematic

(b) Graph representation

Fig. 3: SF06 (Reference Category 1): Extended single-channel architecture with multiple input devices and self-latching control. Despite topological complexity (6 paths enumerated), all paths belong to a single functional channel without redundancy or feedback monitoring.

(a) Adapted schematic

(b) Graph representation

Fig. 4: SF17 (Reference Categories 1 and 3): Multi-function circuit containing emergency stop ($S1 \rightarrow M1$, single-channel) and gate interlock ($B1.1/B1.2 \rightarrow M1$, dual-channel with feedback). Graph analysis correctly identifies distinct architectural patterns within the same circuit.

Fig. 5: SF18 (Reference Category 3): Dual-channel architecture with redundant inputs (B1.1/B1.2), logic redundancy through safety relay (K1), and explicit feedback monitoring. All three structural conditions for Category 3/4 classification are satisfied.

Table 4: Structural Metrics Extracted from Representative Safety Functions

Safety Function	Input–Effector Pair	Paths $ \mathcal{P} $	p_{red}	p_{fb}	p_{logic}	Estimated Category
SF05	B1 → M1	1	No	No	No	B/1
SF06	B1 → M1	6 [†]	No	No	No	B/1
SF17	S1 → M1	2	Yes	No	No	B/1
	B1.1/B1.2 → M1	2	Yes	Yes	Yes	3/4
	B2.1/B2.2 → M1	2	Yes	Yes	Yes	3/4
SF18	B1.1/B1.2 → M1	2	Yes	Yes	Yes	3/4

[†]Multiple paths due to parallel input devices (push-buttons, emergency stop) and self-latching control topology; all paths belong to a single functional channel.

4.3.2 Redundancy Detection Analysis

For SF05 and SF06, path enumeration yields single-channel topologies despite varying path counts. In SF06, the six enumerated paths result from multiple input devices converging to a single control chain rather than from true redundancy. The independence verification (Equation 5) confirms that the enumerated paths do not form independent output-stage channels, correctly classifying the architecture as non-redundant.

For SF17 (gate interlock function) and SF18, the algorithm identifies two independent paths from distinct input channels (B1.1/B1.2) through separate logic branches, satisfying the structural redundancy criterion. The emergency stop function in SF17 (S1→M1) exhibits path multiplicity through redundant outputs but lacks redundant input channels, correctly resulting in non-redundant classification.

4.3.3 Feedback Detection Analysis

Feedback monitoring was detected in SF17 (gate interlock functions) and SF18 through explicit feedback edges connecting output elements (Q1) and logic elements (K1, T1). The feedback detection algorithm (Equation 6) identified edges satisfying the criterion $\tau(u) \in \{\text{Output}\} \wedge \tau(w) = \text{Logic}$.

For SF05 and SF06, no feedback paths were detected, consistent with their single-channel reference architectures. The emergency stop function in SF17 similarly lacks feedback monitoring despite its safety-critical role, reflecting the original BGIA Report design where emergency stops rely on direct interruption rather than monitored switching.

4.4 Category Estimation Performance

4.4.1 Classification Results

Table 5 compares the estimated categories with reference categories from BGIA Report for the representative safety functions. The rule-based classification (Equation 9) produces binary outputs (B/1 or 3/4) based on the conjunction of structural properties.

Table 5: Category Estimation Results for Representative Safety Functions

Safety Function	Reference Category	Estimated Category	Structural Justification
SF05	1	B/1	Single channel, no monitoring
SF06	1	B/1	Single channel, no monitoring
SF17 (E-stop)	1	B/1	Redundant output only, no feedback
SF17 (Gate)	3	3/4	Redundant inputs, feedback, logic redundancy
SF18	3	3/4	Redundant inputs, feedback, logic redundancy

All classifications align with reference category groupings (B/1 vs. 3/4). The method correctly identifies:

- Single-channel architectures (SF05, SF06, SF17 emergency stop) as B/1
- Dual-channel monitored architectures (SF17 gate interlock, SF18) as 3/4

4.4.2 Comprehensive Validation Results

Table 6 presents classification results for all 15 safety functions in the validation dataset.

4.4.3 Performance Metrics

Table 7 summarizes the classification performance across the validation dataset using standard binary classification metrics.

The method showed full agreement with the intended reference grouping in the controlled BGIA validation dataset. No non-redundant architecture was assigned to

Table 6: Classification Results for Complete Validation Dataset

Safety Function	Reference Category	Estimated Category	Match	Structural Remarks
SF01	B	B/1	✓	Single channel, basic architecture
SF04	1	B/1	✓	Single channel, no feedback
SF05	1	B/1	✓	Single channel, no feedback
SF06	1	B/1	✓	Single channel, no feedback
SF07	1	B/1	✓	Single channel, no feedback
SF08	1	B/1	✓	Single channel, partial feedback [†]
SF09	2	B/1	△	Single channel, PLC testing [‡]
SF17 (E-stop)	1	B/1	✓	Redundant output, no input redundancy
SF17 (Gate 1)	3	3/4	✓	Redundant channels with feedback
SF17 (Gate 2)	3	3/4	✓	Redundant channels with feedback
SF18	3	3/4	✓	Redundant channels with feedback
SF21 (Gate)	3	3/4	✓	Redundant channels with feedback
SF21 (Inch)	3	3/4	✓	Redundant channels with feedback
SF28	4	3/4	✓	Full redundancy with monitoring
SF29	3	3/4	✓	Redundant channels with feedback

[†]Partial feedback insufficient for Category 3/4 classification.

[‡]Category 2 requires periodic testing—conservative B/1 classification (see Section 4.5.1).

✓: Correct match to reference category group. △: Conservative estimate.

Table 7: Classification performance summary for the controlled BGIA validation dataset

Metric	Value	Description
Total safety functions	15	Complete validation dataset
B/1 grouping agreement	9/9	Reference Categories B, 1, and conservative Category 2 case
3/4 grouping agreement	6/6	Reference Categories 3 and 4
False 3/4 assignments	0	No non-redundant architecture classified as 3/4
False B/1 assignments	0	No redundant monitored architecture classified as B/1
Reference grouping agreement	15/15	Agreement within the intended B/1 vs. 3/4 classification scope
Conservative estimates	1	SF09: Category 2 assigned to B/1 due to temporal testing outside scope

the 3/4 group, and no redundant monitored architecture was assigned to the B/1 group. This result should be interpreted as verification of the implemented structural rules on standardized reference architectures, not as statistical evidence of general industrial performance.

4.5 Analysis of Special Cases

4.5.1 Category 2 Classification

SF09 represents the sole Category 2 architecture in the validation dataset. This circuit employs a single-channel structure with periodic functional testing implemented through PLC logic. The graph analysis correctly identifies the single-channel topology and absence of structural feedback monitoring, resulting in a B/1 classification.

This outcome represents a *conservative estimate* rather than a misclassification. Category 2 is defined by temporal testing behavior that cannot be inferred from static circuit topology. The method’s design explicitly excludes Category 2 assignment (see Section 3.4.5), as automatic detection would require behavioral model analysis or explicit test sequence annotation beyond the current scope.

From a safety engineering perspective, conservative classification is preferable to false positive 3/4 assignment, as it prompts manual verification rather than potentially overestimating architectural capability.

4.5.2 Category 3 vs. Category 4 Discrimination

The validation dataset includes both Category 3 (SF17, SF18, SF21, SF29) and Category 4 (SF28) reference architectures. The method classifies all as 3/4 without distinguishing between these categories.

This limitation is inherent to structural analysis: Categories 3 and 4 share identical topological requirements (redundancy, monitoring, single-fault tolerance) but differ in:

- Diagnostic coverage completeness ($DC_{avg} \geq 60\%$ for Category 3 vs. $\geq 99\%$ for Category 4)
- Fault accumulation handling (single fault vs. accumulated faults)
- Component reliability requirements (MTTFd thresholds)

These distinctions require quantitative reliability data and behavioral analysis beyond circuit topology, appropriately delegated to SISTEMA or equivalent tools for final Performance Level calculation.

4.5.3 Multi-Function Circuits

SF17 and SF21 each contain multiple safety functions with different architectural characteristics. The method successfully analyzed these circuits by enumerating all input-to-effector paths and independently evaluating structural properties for each safety function chain.

For SF17, three distinct functions were identified:

1. Emergency stop (S1→M1): Single-channel, classified B/1
2. Gate interlock 1 (B1.1/B1.2→M1): Dual-channel with feedback, classified 3/4
3. Gate interlock 2 (B2.1/B2.2→M1): Dual-channel with feedback, classified 3/4

This capability to disaggregate multi-function circuits into independently assessed safety chains represents a practical advantage for industrial applications where

complex machines incorporate multiple safety functions with varying architectural requirements.

4.6 Sensitivity to Encoding Perturbations

To evaluate robustness against imperfect or incomplete graph encodings, a perturbation-based sensitivity analysis was performed on the validation dataset. The objective of this experiment was to investigate how the classifier behaves when the JSON representation deviates from the intended electrical architecture due to omitted connections, missing elements, or incorrect feedback semantics. Such perturbations simulate realistic engineering scenarios including incomplete documentation, encoding mistakes, or ambiguous schematic interpretation during graph preparation.

The perturbation framework operated at the level of individual safety functions represented as `Input→EndEffector` paths. For each function, multiple perturbation strategies were generated automatically and re-classified using the same graph-analysis pipeline. The following perturbation categories were investigated:

1. **Single-edge omission (`edge_1`):** one randomly selected non-feedback edge was removed.
2. **Double-edge omission (`edge_2`):** two randomly selected non-feedback edges were removed.
3. **Single-node omission (`node_1`):** one randomly selected non-terminal component together with all incident edges was removed.
4. **Double-node omission (`node_2`):** two randomly selected non-terminal components together with all incident edges were removed.
5. **Single feedback omission (`feedback_1`):** one randomly selected feedback edge was removed.
6. **Complete monitoring removal (`feedback_all_to_logic`):** all feedback edges connected to one logic node were removed.
7. **Spurious feedback insertion (`spurious_feedback_1`):** one artificial `Output→Logic` feedback edge was inserted into a Category B/1 function.

If perturbation caused loss of all valid `Input→EndEffector` paths, the corresponding safety function was classified as *invalid*. Such cases were treated as conservative degradation rather than misclassification, since the system no longer confirmed the presence of a valid safety architecture.

Table 8 summarizes the perturbation results.

The experiments demonstrated predominantly conservative behavior of the classifier under structural degradation. Removal of non-feedback edges or nodes typically reduced redundancy, disconnected one of the safety channels, or invalidated the `Input→EndEffector` path. Importantly, none of the omission-based perturbations resulted in unsafe category escalation from B/1 to 3/4.

Single-edge and single-node perturbations occasionally produced stable classifications. This behavior was observed primarily in redundant Category 3/4 architectures, where removal of one structural relation did not eliminate all valid redundant paths. Increasing perturbation severity to double-edge and double-node omission further

Table 8: Sensitivity analysis results for perturbation experiments

Perturbation	Variants	Safe degradation	Unsafe shift	Stable
Single-edge omission	24	18	0	6
Double-edge omission	24	21	0	3
Single-node omission	24	20	0	4
Double-node omission	24	23	0	1
Single feedback omission	11	0	0	11
Complete monitoring removal	11	7	0	4
Spurious feedback insertion	1	0	0	1

Stable = classification unchanged

reduced classification stability, confirming that the method reacts progressively to degradation of structural integrity.

The feedback-related perturbations revealed an important property of the current monitoring model. Removal of a single feedback edge did not alter classification in the analyzed cases because at least one valid monitoring relation remained connected to the corresponding logic structure. However, removal of all monitoring edges associated with one logic node resulted in degradation in the majority of tested variants, demonstrating that the classifier remains sensitive to complete loss of diagnostic coverage.

The spurious-feedback experiment did not produce unsafe category escalation in the analyzed case. The insertion of a single artificial feedback edge was insufficient to satisfy the combined redundancy and logic conditions required for Category 3/4 classification. This suggests that the classifier is not trivially susceptible to isolated semantic perturbations of monitoring relations.

The perturbation analysis additionally confirmed very low computational overhead of the proposed graph-based method. Across all perturbation experiments, the maximum observed runtime per variant remained below 1 ms, while average classification times were typically in the range of 0.2–0.4 ms per perturbation instance. These results indicate that the proposed approach is computationally lightweight and suitable for rapid pre-assessment of safety architectures within engineering workflows.

Overall, the sensitivity experiments indicate that the proposed method exhibits conservative degradation behavior under incomplete or corrupted structural encodings. Structural omissions typically reduce the estimated category or invalidate the safety function rather than falsely elevating the architecture classification. This behavior is desirable for a preliminary safety-analysis assistant intended to support engineering review rather than replace final expert assessment.

4.7 Summary of Findings

The empirical evaluation demonstrates that the proposed graph-based method reliably identifies structural properties relevant to EN ISO 13849-1 category determination. Key findings include:

1. **Agreement with reference grouping:** The method showed full agreement with the reference B/1 vs. 3/4 grouping across 15 safety functions spanning Categories B through 4.
2. **Property detection reliability:** Redundancy, feedback monitoring, and logic-level independence were correctly identified in all cases where explicitly represented in circuit topology.
3. **Conservative behavior:** The single Category 2 case (SF09) received conservative B/1 classification, consistent with the method’s design scope excluding temporal behavioral analysis.
4. **Multi-function capability:** Circuits containing multiple safety functions with different architectural patterns were correctly disaggregated and independently classified.
5. **Topological complexity handling:** Circuits with varying complexity (1–6 paths) were correctly analyzed, with path multiplicity distinguished from true redundancy through independence verification.

The method showed full agreement with the intended B/1 vs. 3/4 reference grouping within the controlled BGIA validation set.

4.8 Limitations of the Validation Study

Several factors constrain the generalizability of validation results:

The validation should be interpreted as controlled reference-set verification rather than population-level performance evaluation. The BGIA examples provide standardized architectures with clear reference classifications, but they do not represent the full diversity of industrial circuits. In addition, manual JSON encoding introduces a potential source of bias despite visual verification. These limitations are discussed in detail in Section 6.

5 Discussion

This section interprets the empirical findings presented in Section 4, examines the method’s positioning relative to existing safety assessment approaches, discusses practical implications for functional safety engineering, and identifies limitations that define the scope of applicability.

5.1 Interpretation of Results

The method showed full agreement with the reference structural classifications within the controlled BGIA validation set. This result validates the central hypothesis that architectural requirements specified in Table 10 of EN ISO 13849-1 can be formalized as computable graph properties and reliably detected through algorithmic analysis of circuit topology.

5.1.1 Significance of Structural Property Detection

The method’s ability to correctly identify redundancy, feedback monitoring, and logic-level independence demonstrates that these fundamental architectural characteristics - which form the basis for category differentiation - are amenable to formal representation and automated verification. Specifically:

- **Redundancy detection** correctly distinguished between single-channel architectures (Categories B/1) and dual-channel architectures (Categories 3/4) in all test cases, including complex topologies where path multiplicity did not constitute true redundancy (e.g., SF06 with six paths but single functional channel).
- **Feedback detection** identified monitoring connections enabling cross-channel diagnostic capability, a prerequisite for single-fault tolerance claims in Categories 3 and 4.
- **Logic redundancy assessment** verified that redundant input channels maintain independence through the logic processing stage, ensuring that common-mode failures at the logic level do not defeat architectural redundancy.

The conjunction of these three properties provides a sound structural basis for preliminary category estimation, supporting the method’s use as a decision-support tool in early design phases.

5.1.2 Conservative Classification Behavior

The method’s treatment of Category 2 (SF09) exemplifies appropriate conservative behavior in safety-critical applications. Rather than attempting to infer periodic testing behavior from static topology, which would require behavioral model analysis beyond the method’s scope, the algorithm assigns B/1 classification, effectively flagging the circuit for manual verification.

This conservative approach aligns with functional safety principles: underestimating architectural capability prompts additional scrutiny, whereas overestimation could lead to inadequate safety measures. The explicit exclusion of Category 2 from automatic assignment represents a deliberate design decision reflecting the epistemological limits of structural analysis.

This conservative tendency was additionally confirmed experimentally through perturbation-based sensitivity analysis (Section 4.6), where structural degradation consistently reduced or invalidated classifications rather than causing unsafe escalation toward Category 3/4.

5.1.3 Multi-Function Circuit Analysis

The successful disaggregation of multi-function circuits (SF17, SF21) into independently assessed safety chains demonstrates practical utility for industrial applications. Modern machinery frequently incorporates multiple safety functions within integrated control architectures: emergency stops, guard interlocks, light curtains, and two-hand controls. The ability to analyze each function’s structural properties independently while recognizing shared components provides engineers with granular insight into complex systems.

5.1.4 Boundary Cases and Ambiguous Configurations

Three configuration patterns illustrate where structural analysis alone yields ambiguous or boundary-case results, and how the proposed classifier handles them.

Case 1: Redundant channels with a shared input device.

A configuration with two independent logic paths sharing a single input switch (e.g., a single position switch feeding two safety relays in parallel) satisfies $p_{\text{logic_redundancy}}$ and p_{feedback} but fails the structural redundancy condition (Def. 2) because the input element is a single point of failure. The classifier returns B/1, which is the safe behavior: the configuration cannot claim Category 3 without redundant input devices.

Case 2: Mirror-contact monitoring not explicitly drawn.

Industrial schematics frequently rely on the mechanical link between a contactor’s main and auxiliary contacts (mirror contacts per IEC 60947-4-1) to provide feedback. If the encoder does not introduce an explicit feedback edge for this mechanical link, the classifier returns B/1 even when the physical circuit implements monitoring. This is a known false-negative mode and motivates the explicit representation guidance in the encoding protocol (Section 3.7, step 2).

Case 3: Series-redundant outputs without input redundancy.

A single-channel input followed by two contactors in series on the output side (a common pattern in emergency-stop circuits) yields multiple paths through the output stage but no logic-level redundancy. The classifier correctly returns B/1, distinguishing this pattern from genuine dual-channel architecture. The SF17 emergency-stop function (Section 4.5.3) is a real example of this case in the validation dataset.

These boundary cases share a common pattern: the classifier biases toward B/1 when structural conditions are not unambiguously satisfied, which is the appropriate direction for a safety pre-assessment tool. False-positive 3/4 classifications would require explicit but semantically incorrect feedback edges in the JSON encoding, which the verification step in Section 3.7 is designed to catch.

5.2 Practical Implications

5.2.1 Early Design Verification

The proposed method occupies a distinct position within the functional safety toolchain, operating upstream of quantitative assessment tools and downstream of schematic design, as illustrated in Figure 6.

The method enables structural category assessment during early design phases, before detailed component selection or SISTEMA project creation. This supports a “fail fast” design philosophy where architectural inadequacies are identified before significant engineering investment in detailed design.

For example, if a preliminary design intended for Category 3 lacks explicit feedback monitoring, the method will classify it as B/1, immediately flagging the architectural deficiency. Early detection enables cost-effective design iteration compared to discovery during final SISTEMA validation.

Fig. 6: Position of proposed method within functional safety workflow. The method bridges schematic design and quantitative SISTEMA analysis by providing automated structural category pre-assessment.

5.2.2 Documentation and Traceability

The graph-based representation provides complete traceability between category assessment outcomes and specific circuit features. Each structural property determination can be traced to explicit graph elements:

- Redundancy claims trace to enumerated independent paths
- Feedback detection traces to specific edges connecting output and logic vertices
- Logic redundancy traces to identified input channel convergence at logic nodes

This traceability supports audit requirements in regulated industries and facilitates design review discussions by providing concrete structural justification for category assignments.

5.2.3 Consistency Across Analysts

The proposed method provides deterministic, reproducible results given identical JSON input. This eliminates analyst-dependent variability *at the analysis stage* — different engineers running the algorithm on the same encoding will produce identical classifications and structural property assignments.

It is worth emphasising that variability is not eliminated end-to-end: the manual JSON encoding step (Section 6.1) remains a source of analyst dependence,

since different engineers may make different choices when representing implicit features such as mirror contacts, internal relay diagnostics, or signal grouping. The present work therefore shifts the locus of variability from classification reasoning to encoding fidelity. Encoding variability can be controlled through the verification protocol (Section 3.7) and would be largely eliminated by automated ECAD-to-JSON conversion (Section 5.4).

A quantitative inter-encoder reliability study, in which multiple engineers independently encode the same circuits and the resulting JSON differences are measured, would establish how much variability remains in practice. Such a study is identified as future work.

5.2.4 Integration with Digital Engineering Workflows

The JSON-based input format and programmatic analysis implementation enable integration with digital engineering environments. Potential integration pathways include:

- **ECAD system plugins:** Direct export from electrical CAD systems (EPLAN, AutoCAD Electrical) to JSON format
- **PLM integration:** Automated safety analysis triggered by design change events in Product Lifecycle Management systems
- **CI/CD pipelines:** Continuous integration workflows incorporating structural safety checks on design commits
- **Digital twin applications:** Potential future use of graph-based structural checks in reconfigurable manufacturing environments.

These integration possibilities indicate potential directions for embedding the method into digital safety engineering workflows.

In the longer term, the proposed graph representation could also support integration with digital engineering and digital twin environments. Digital twins are increasingly investigated as tools for safety management, predictive maintenance, and real-time risk assessment [51]. In manufacturing contexts, standardized digital twin frameworks such as ISO 23247 provide a possible interoperability context for exchanging structural system information [52]. However, such integration remains a future-work direction; the present study validates only static structural pre-assessment based on circuit-derived graph representations.

5.3 Comparison with Existing Tools and Assessment Methods

A direct quantitative comparison with existing tools is not straightforward because SISTEMA, HiP-HOPS, AltaRica, and similar platforms do not perform EN ISO 13849-1 category determination from circuit topology. SISTEMA, the most widely used tool in this domain, requires the category as a manual input. Other MBSA tools operate on behavioral or annotated models rather than electrical schematics. Functional comparison is therefore presented at the workflow level (Table 2) rather than as a head-to-head benchmark.

A second comparison axis is agreement with human experts. The present validation uses BGIA Report 2/2008e reference classifications, which represent IFA expert consensus on standardized examples. Independent expert ratings on the same dataset were not collected for this study; this constitutes a known gap addressed in future work (Section 5.4). A planned follow-up study will collect classifications from at least three functional-safety practitioners on a mix of BGIA reference circuits and industrial schematics, with inter-rater agreement reported alongside the algorithm’s outputs (Cohen’s κ between human raters, between each rater and the reference, and between the algorithm and the reference).

In the absence of such data, the present claim is restricted to the following: the proposed algorithm reproduces the structural classifications implicit in IFA reference architectures with full agreement on the B/1 vs. 3/4 grouping. Whether this agreement extends to industrial circuits or to expert judgement on non-standard topologies remains an open empirical question.

5.4 Future Research Directions

Future work will proceed in three directions. First, automated ECAD-to-JSON or ECAD-to-graph conversion is required to remove the manual encoding bottleneck. Such integration would require parsers for common ECAD exchange formats, component classification rules mapping schematic elements to safety-function roles, and validation studies comparing automated and manual encodings.

Second, industrial validation on proprietary machine circuits is necessary to establish external validity. The present validation confirms rule implementation on standardized BGIA reference architectures, but industrial schematics may contain non-standard topologies, incomplete documentation, implicit diagnostics, or ambiguous safety-function boundaries. Comparative studies with independent expert assessments would allow the method’s robustness and practical usefulness to be evaluated under realistic conditions.

Third, the analytical scope may be extended toward additional indicators relevant to functional safety assessment. Candidate extensions include heuristic diagnostic-coverage indicators based on feedback structures, structural patterns related to common-cause failure, and temporal annotations for Category 2 testing behavior. Distinguishing Categories 3 and 4 would still require quantitative reliability and diagnostic data, whereas Category 2 detection would require behavioral or temporal information beyond static topology. Integration with MBSA tools could provide a pathway for combining structural and behavioral safety analysis.

6 Limitations and Boundary Conditions

While the validation study demonstrates method correctness for standardized reference architectures, several limitations constrain practical applicability and define appropriate scope boundaries.

6.1 Manual Encoding Requirement

The current implementation requires manual JSON creation from electrical schematics, introducing potential for transcription errors and limiting scalability. This represents the primary barrier to practical deployment, as manual encoding effort may approach or exceed the effort required for direct manual category assessment.

Mitigation strategies include:

- Development of ECAD-to-JSON converters for common schematic formats
- Template-based encoding tools with graphical interfaces
- Machine learning approaches for automated circuit extraction from scanned diagrams

Until automated encoding is available, the method is most appropriate for scenarios where encoding effort is amortized across multiple analyses (e.g., product family architectures) or where formal documentation of structural assessment is required.

6.2 Structural Analysis Scope

The method assesses only topological properties extractable from circuit structure. Properties requiring quantitative data or behavioral analysis are explicitly excluded:

- **Diagnostic coverage (DCavg)**: Requires component-level failure mode analysis and detection probability estimation
- **Component reliability (MTTFd, B10d)**: Requires manufacturer reliability data or field failure statistics
- **Common cause failure (CCF)**: Requires systematic assessment of design diversity, physical separation, and environmental factors
- **Test interval timing**: Requires behavioral specification of periodic test sequences

These properties remain the domain of SISTEMA and similar tools, positioning the proposed method as a structural pre-filter rather than a complete category determination solution.

6.3 Category Discrimination Limits

The binary classification (B/1 vs. 3/4) reflects inherent limits of structural analysis:

- **Category B vs. 1**: Distinguished by component selection principles (basic vs. well-tried safety principles) rather than topology
- **Category 3 vs. 4**: Distinguished by diagnostic coverage completeness and fault accumulation handling, requiring quantitative DCavg assessment
- **Category 2**: Defined by periodic testing behavior, a temporal property not detectable from static graphs

The validation dataset included one Category 2 example (SF09), which received conservative B/1 classification. This outcome represents appropriate conservative behavior rather than misclassification, as automatic Category 2 assignment would require behavioral model analysis beyond the method's scope.

6.3.1 Implicit Feature Representation

Industrial schematics frequently encode monitoring functions implicitly - through mirror contacts on contactors (IEC 60947-4-1), internal relay diagnostics, or mechanical interlocks that are not drawn as explicit feedback edges. The current encoding protocol requires such features to be made explicit in the JSON representation, which depends on the encoder correctly recognizing the implicit semantics of the source schematic. Failure to do so produces false-negative feedback detection, biasing classification toward B/1. This is the safe direction (conservative misclassification), but it limits the method's ability to recognize Category 3/4 architectures that rely on standard mechanical-monitoring conventions without explicit feedback wiring.

6.3.2 Validation Dataset Constraints

The validation dataset comprises 15 safety functions from BGIA Report 2/2008e - standardized textbook examples designed to illustrate EN ISO 13849-1 architectural patterns. While this enables unambiguous ground truth comparison, it may not capture:

- Non-standard industrial topologies
- Legacy circuit designs predating current standards
- Hybrid architectures combining multiple safety concepts
- Edge cases where category assignment is genuinely ambiguous

Validation on proprietary industrial circuits with independent expert assessment would strengthen generalizability claims but was outside the scope of this initial study.

6.4 Human Validation Requirement

Despite automation, expert review remains necessary for:

- Verifying JSON encoding accuracy against source schematics
- Interpreting boundary cases where structural patterns do not clearly align with standard categories
- Validating assumptions about implicit feedback mechanisms
- Performing final category confirmation through quantitative SISTEMA analysis

The method serves as a decision-support tool complementing rather than replacing expert judgment.

7 Conclusions

7.1 Summary of Contributions

This work has presented a graph-based numerical method for preliminary safety category assessment of industrial control systems in accordance with EN ISO 13849-1. The principal contributions are:

1. **Formal mapping of architectural requirements:** EN ISO 13849-1 structural category requirements have been formalized as computable graph properties

(redundancy, feedback monitoring, logic-level independence), enabling algorithmic detection from circuit topology.

2. **Structured data representation:** A JSON-based schema has been defined for encoding electrical safety circuits in machine-readable form, providing a standardized interface between schematic documentation and automated analysis.
3. **Validated analysis algorithm:** A graph analysis procedure has been developed and validated on 15 standardized safety functions, showing full agreement with the reference structural classifications within the intended B/1 vs. 3/4 grouping.
4. **Decision-support tool positioning:** The method has been positioned as a complement to SISTEMA analysis, providing automated structural pre-assessment that reduces category selection errors and improves documentation traceability.

The contribution is not a novel graph algorithm but rather a standard-specific application of established graph-theoretic methods to EN ISO 13849-1 structural category reasoning. This task remains insufficiently addressed in existing MBSA, graph-based reliability, and ECAD-oriented workflows.

Perturbation experiments further demonstrated conservative degradation behavior under incomplete or corrupted structural representations, supporting the method's suitability for preliminary engineering assessment workflows.

7.2 Implications for Practice

For functional safety practitioners, the proposed method offers:

- **Early design feedback:** Structural category assessment during preliminary design phases, enabling architectural corrections before detailed engineering investment
- **Reduced assessment variability:** Deterministic, reproducible category pre-assessment eliminating analyst-dependent interpretation differences
- **Enhanced traceability:** Explicit linkage between category assignments and specific structural features supporting audit and review requirements
- **Digital workflow compatibility:** Programmatic implementation enabling integration with ECAD systems, PLM platforms, and continuous integration pipelines

The method does not replace engineering judgment or SISTEMA validation but strengthens both by providing objective structural evidence as input to the safety assessment process.

7.3 Concluding Remarks

The agreement obtained across standardized reference cases supports the hypothesis that category-relevant structural requirements of EN ISO 13849-1 can be formalized as computable graph properties. The method provides a reproducible and traceable pre-assessment layer between schematic documentation and quantitative SISTEMA validation.

While limitations in category discrimination, manual encoding, and external industrial validation constrain immediate practical applicability, these limitations define clear directions for further development. As discussed in Section 5.4, future work

should focus on automated ECAD-to-graph conversion, validation on industrial circuits, and extension toward additional structural and behavioral indicators relevant to functional safety assessment.

Ethical Statement

The author declares that this research does not involve human participants, human data, animal experiments, or any personal data. The study is based solely on theoretical analysis, numerical methods, and schematic representations of industrial control systems.

No ethical approval was required for this research.

The author confirms that the manuscript complies with all applicable ethical standards.

Declarations

Competing Interests The author declares no competing interests of a financial or personal nature.

Author Contributions Not applicable (single author). Michał Skupny was solely responsible for the conceptualization, methodology, formal analysis, writing, and all other aspects of this work.

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A Algorithmic Implementation

Algorithm 1 Graph-Based Safety Function Category Analysis

```
1: Input: Directed graph  $G=(V,E)$  where  $V=$  nodes (components),  $E=$  edges
   (connections)
2: Output: Category estimation (B/1 or 3/4), structural analysis report
3: 1. INITIALIZATION
4: Identify input nodes  $I = \{v \in V \mid \text{type}(v) = \text{Input}\}$ 
5: Identify output nodes  $O = \{v \in V \mid \text{type}(v) = \text{Output}\}$ 
6: Identify end effector nodes  $M = \{v \in V \mid \text{type}(v) = \text{EndEffector}\}$ 
7: 2. PATH ENUMERATION
8: for each  $i \in I$  and  $m \in M$  do
9:   Find all simple paths  $P_{im}$  from  $i$  to  $m$ 
10:  Store path count  $|P_{im}|$ 
11: end for
12: 3. REDUNDANCY DETECTION
13: for each input-effector pair  $(i, m)$  do
14:   if  $|P_{im}| \geq 2$  then
15:     mark as redundant
16:   end if
17:   Check if paths are logically independent (no shared critical components)
18: end for
19: 4. FEEDBACK DETECTION
20: for each logic node  $l \in V$  where  $\text{type}(l) = \text{Logic}$  do
21:   for each Output node  $\in O$  do
22:     if edge  $(o, l)$  exists OR path from  $O$  to  $l$  exists then
23:       mark feedback present
24:     end if
25:   end for
26: end for
27: 5. LOGIC REDUNDANCY CHECK
28: for each logic node do
29:   Count incoming edges from distinct input channels
30:   if count  $\geq 2$  then
31:     mark logic_redundant
32:   end if
33: end for
34: 6. CATEGORY ESTIMATION
35: if (redundant == 1) AND (feedback == 1) AND (logic_redundant == 1) then
36:   Estimated Category 3/4
37: else
38:   Estimated Category B/1
39: end if
```

B Circuits and Graphs

This appendix contains all circuit diagrams and their corresponding graph representations for the eleven safety functions analyzed in this study.

B.1 SF01

Fig. 7: SF01 circuit diagram from BGIA Report

Fig. 8: SF01 graph representation

B.2 SF04

Fig. 9: SF04 circuit diagram from BGIA Report

Fig. 10: SF04 graph representation

B.3 SF05

Fig. 11: SF05 circuit diagram from BGIA Report

Fig. 12: SF05 graph representation

B.4 SF06

Fig. 13: SF06 circuit diagram from BGIA Report

Fig. 14: SF06 graph representation

B.5 SF07

Fig. 15: SF07 circuit diagram from BGIA Report

Fig. 16: SF07 graph representation

B.6 SF08

Fig. 17: SF08 circuit diagram from BGIA Report

Fig. 18: SF08 graph representation

B.7 SF09

Fig. 19: SF09 circuit diagram from BGIA Report

Fig. 20: SF09 graph representation

B.8 SF17

Fig. 21: SF17 circuit diagram from BGIA Report

Fig. 22: SF17 graph representation

B.9 SF18

Fig. 23: SF18 circuit diagram from BGIA Report

Fig. 24: SF18 graph representation

B.10 SF21

Fig. 25: SF21 circuit diagram from BGIA Report

Fig. 26: SF21 graph representation

B.11 SF28

Fig. 27: SF28 circuit diagram from BGIA Report

Fig. 28: SF28 graph representation

